

Stability of inland vessels in extremely low water levels

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ABSTRACT

The paper addresses the assessment of intact and damage stability of Western European inland dry cargo vessels equipped with “additional buoyancy bodies”. Additional buoyancy bodies, such as the “pipe-based buoyancy” examined in this study, are intended for increase of buoyancy and, thus, cargo-carrying capacity of inland vessels sailing at low draughts in extremely low water levels. The use of additional buoyancy bodies, however, may imply an increased risk of stability-related hazards atypical for navigation in regular water levels. On the other hand, neither low water levels nor additional buoyancy bodies are considered by the present stability regulations. The analysis presented in the paper shows that compliance with the applicable intact and damage stability rules may be achieved with the standard loading practices, but that this may be insufficient to avoid grounding in particularly low water. The loss of one additional buoyancy body may be exceptionally dangerous, as it could lead to a total stability failure, grounding of the vessel, loss of cargo, and obstruction of navigation. The paper, thus, investigates the stability-related operational measures which could be employed to counter the risks triggered by navigation in extremely low water levels.

Keywords: *Inland vessels, Additional buoyancy bodies, Low water levels, NOVIMOVE.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The droughts in the summer of 2018 severely disrupted supply chains in Western Europe, which resulted in serious negative economic consequences: it is estimated that the losses of the manufacturing industry in Germany alone amounted to 4.7 billion EUR (Schweighofer et al., 2022). Recent research suggests that such extreme low-water events will be more frequent in the future. In fact, even more extreme low water levels were recorded on the Western European inland waterways already in 2022. In response, the creation of regional and national strategies addressing the problem of inland navigation in extremely low water levels was intensified. Such strategies consider different logistics, waterway management, and ship technology measures (see, for instance, Friedhoff et al., 2022). This paper

focuses on technical solutions examined within the Horizon 2020 project NOVIMOVE (Novel inland waterway transport concepts for moving freight effectively), intended for improvement of efficiency of existing inland dry cargo / container vessels on the Rhine, and on the related implications for intact and damage stability performance of such vessels in extreme low-water conditions.

Some of the proposed technical solutions imply the increase of buoyancy (and, thus, cargo-carrying capacity) of ships sailing at low draughts by means of the so-called “additional buoyancy bodies” which would be temporarily deployed in shallow-water sectors. This idea is not entirely new: additional buoyancy bodies were used in the Netherlands already in the 17th century to assist ships in sailing over the shallows of the nowadays IJsselmeer, see Boven & Hoving (2009). Iqbal et al.

(2008) considered the use of additional inflatable buoyancy to improve intact stability of small passenger ferries in Bangladesh. An overview of the contemporary solutions and patents intended for increase of buoyancy is given in Friedhoff et al. (2020).

One of the concepts of additional buoyancy bodies is the “pipe-based buoyancy” (PBB) consisting of fully rigid, steel cylindrical bodies with conical ends temporarily connected to the ship hull sides, see Figure 1. This paper addresses intact and damage stability of a standard inland container vessel of CEMT Class Va¹ (the so-called Large Rhine vessel) equipped with PBB.

Figure 1. Principal arrangement of the pipe-based buoyancy (PBB)

Operational conditions in extremely low water levels may imply sailing with under-keel clearance as little as 0.3 m and in reduced fairway width, which increases the likelihood of grounding, collision, and allision. Therefore, stability failures may not be limited to large heel angles; for instance, even the relatively small angles of heel may cause the vessel grounding and subsequent suspension of traffic on the waterway. Neither the low-water operational conditions, nor the additional buoyancy bodies are specifically addressed by the current safety regulations for inland navigation.

Therefore, the paper investigates the “operational measures” for a sample vessel with additional buoyancy bodies from the ship stability point of view, with reference to the applicable regulations and the specific navigation conditions. In addition to calculating the maximum vertical center of gravity KG_{max} / the minimum metacentric height GM_{min} in compliance with the applicable stability regulations, it is examined if there are scenarios in which the safety of the sample ship equipped with PBB may be jeopardized even though the stability rules are formally being complied with.

¹ For CEMT classification of inland vessels in Europe see CEMT (1992).

2. APPLICABLE REGULATIONS

Intact stability of inland container vessels in Western Europe should conform to the requirements of ES-TRIN (“European Standard Laying Down Technical Requirements for Inland Navigation Vessels”), Chapter 27, see CESNI (2023). The standards (related to minimum metacentric height) differ depending on whether the ship transports “non-secured” or “secured” containers. The minimum metacentric height GM_{min} must not be below 1 m (in case the ship carries non-secured containers) or 0.5 m (in case the ship carries secured containers). When exposed to the simultaneous action of heeling moments due to turn (M_{dr}) and beam wind (M_w), the static angle of heel should not be greater than either the angle at which the deck edge enters the water (φ_{deck}) or 5° , whichever is less (Figure 2). Since inland container vessels have a large open cargo hold, it is required to conduct intact stability calculations assuming the presence of rainwater in cargo hold. Additionally, all intact stability calculations are carried out with 50% of supplies (in practice, mainly fuel and fresh water).

Figure 2. Intact stability requirements for inland container vessels carrying non-secured containers according to ES-TRIN (CESNI, 2023)

Damage stability assessment for this type of vessels is not mandatory unless:

- they carry dangerous cargo, in which case they are subject to the ADN (“European Agreement concerning the International Carriage of Dangerous Goods by Inland Waterways”) rules, Chapter 9 (see UNECE, 2023), or
- they are longer than 110 m, in which case they are subject to ES-TRIN, Chapter 28 (CESNI, 2023).

This means that inland container vessels up to 110 m in length, which do not carry dangerous goods, do not have to comply with the damage stability requirements. The damage stability rules of both ADN and ES-TRIN contain deterministic requirements which should be satisfied in the final stage of flooding and in the relevant intermediate stages of flooding following assumed bottom and side damages whose dimensions are prescribed.² Considering inland container vessels, the requirements again differ depending on the securing of the containers. The ADN requirements applicable to container vessels carrying non-secured containers are given in Figure 3. Static angle of heel in the final stage of flooding should not be greater than 5°. The area under the righting lever beyond the static equilibrium and up to the angle at which the first unprotected opening enters the water (φ_H) or 10° (whichever is less) should not be less than 0.0065 mrad. Two-compartment standard applies in the longitudinal direction, except in the case of the main engine room which is subject to one-compartment standard only. Bottom damages also imply flooding of adjacent athwartships compartments.

Figure 3. Damage stability requirements for inland container vessels carrying non-secured containers according to ADN (UNECE, 2023)

3. SAMPLE SHIP AND PBB BODIES

The sample ship used in the study is a standard Western European Class Va inland container vessel. The main dimensions of the sample ship and the pipe-based buoyancy bodies are given in Table 1. The body plan of the sample ship is given in

Figure 4; the cross sections are equally spaced at 1 m distance, whereby “0” represents the aftmost station. Such vessels typically load containers in up to four tiers. It is assumed that the ship would carry non-secured containers which may contain dangerous goods. Furthermore, it is assumed that the PBB bodies would be deployed at low water levels when the fully loaded ship would sail at $d_1 = 1.8$ m and $d_2 = 1.2$ m. For the purpose of this study, the PBB bodies are considered to be cylindrical bodies of length L_{PBB} and diameter D_{PBB} (i.e., the conical ends are disregarded for the sake of simplicity of the analysis).

Table 1. Main dimensions of the sample ship without the pipe-based buoyancy (PBB) bodies and the free-floating PBB body

length overall, L_{OA} [m]	109.7
length of the waterline, L_{WL} [m]	109.4
beam, B [m]	11.44
design draught, d [m]	3.2
depth, D [m]	3.68
displacement, Δ [t]	3623.5
maximum ship speed, v [km/h]	18
maximum number of containers, n_{TEU}	208
length of the PBB body, L_{PBB} [m]	80
diameter of the PBB body, D_{PBB} [m]	3
draught of the PBB body, d_{PBB} [m]	0.3
mass of the PBB body, m_{PBB} [t]	30.1

Figure 4. Body plan of the sample ship; $d = 3.2$ m is the design draught of the vessel, while $d_1 = 1.8$ m and $d_2 = 1.2$ m are the operational draughts at which the additional buoyancy bodies would be deployed

The practical benefits of using PBB on the sample ship are summarized in Table 2. At low draughts, the sample ship would be capable of carrying 39% (at $d = 1.8$ m) and 13% (at $d = 1.2$ m) of its cargo capacity at design draught; in addition, in latter case, the ship would not be able to carry the maximum number of containers. After the deployment of PBB, the cargo-carrying capacity of the sample vessel at low draughts increases by 63%

² Curiously, although the damage stability standards for container vessels of ADN and ES-TRIN are the same, the assumed damages differ.

(at $d = 1.8$ m) and by 102% (at $d = 1.2$ m) in comparison to the possible capacity of the same vessel at given draughts without the added buoyancy bodies.

Table 2. Cargo-carrying capacity of the sample ships without and with the pipe-based buoyancy (PBB) bodies

d	m_{cargo} [t]	
	without PBB	with PBB
3.2	2707.6	/
1.8	1046.5	1701.5
1.2	358.8	726.3

4. STABILITY ASSESSMENT

Intact and damage stability assessment of the sample ship equipped with the PBB bodies was carried out at draughts $d = 1.753$ m and $d = 1.149$ m (which correspond to draughts $d = 1.8$ m and $d = 1.2$ m with 50% of supplies) in two-tier and four-tier container arrangement.

Intact stability

The parameters necessary for intact stability calculations which change with the changes of draught and container arrangement are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Parameters necessary for intact stability assessment which depend on the draught and the container arrangement: lateral area exposed to wind A_w and the distance of the centroid of A_w from the waterline l_w

d	tiers	A_w [m ²]	l_w [m]
1.753	4	872.9	4.392
1.149	4	938.1	4.669
1.753	2	450.6	2.159
1.149	2	515.8	2.452

The maximum vertical center of gravity KG_{max} and the minimum metacentric height GM_{min} , calculated in compliance with ES-TRIN regulations for the considered cases are given in Table 4. The results indicate that the sample ship equipped with the PBB bodies would fulfill intact stability requirements with a considerable margin. In all the cases, the limiting values of KG and GM are attained when the vertical center of gravity of the cargo, KG_{cargo} , is very high, outside of the physical boundaries of the cargo.

Therefore, the static angle of heel of the sample ship with the vertical center of gravity corresponding to uniform vertical distribution of

cargo, exposed to the heeling moments defined by the ES-TRIN regulations, is calculated for all cases considered. The results reported in Table 5 show that the heeling angles are negligible. Such results could have been expected; the question is, however, if a ship satisfying intact stability standards could be considered as safe with reference to possible hazards in low water levels.

Table 4. Maximum vertical center of gravity and minimum metacentric height of the sample ship equipped with PBB, and the corresponding vertical center of gravity of the cargo, determined in compliance with the intact stability regulations of ES-TRIN (CESNI, 2023)

d	tiers	KG_{max}	GM_{min}	KG_{cargo}
1.753	4	12.738	2.607	18.531
1.149	4	18.814	4.219	39.966
1.753	2	13.063	2.281	19.029
1.149	2	19.351	3.681	41.173

Table 5. Static angle of heel of the sample ship equipped with PBB, due to heeling moments defined by the intact stability regulations of ES-TRIN (CESNI, 2023), corresponding to uniform vertical distribution of the cargo

d	tiers	KG	GM	KG_{cargo}	ϕ_s
1.753	4	4.41	10.934	5.782	0.6°
1.149	4	3.589	19.444	5.782	0.5°
1.753	2	2.718	12.626	3.191	0.3°
1.149	2	2.435	20.598	3.191	0.3°

Namely, while calculating the GM_{min} values given in Table 4, the condition that the static angle of heel should not be greater than 5° (Figure 2) proved to be the most stringent requirement in all the cases considered. Nevertheless, in extremely low water levels, even the very small angles of heel could lead to a contact with the riverbed and possible grounding. The minimum under-keel clearance (hereinafter marked by ukc) is not restricted by safety regulations (though it is typically considered that $ukc = 0.3$ m is sufficient to avoid contact with the riverbed, considering also the expected squat); it is at discretion of Master to decide whether to sail or not, whereby such decision is typically based on economy considerations (costs associated with inefficient propulsion vs. a business opportunity on the spot market). Indeed, if the sample vessel sailing at $d = 1.753$ m is inclined to 5°, the lowest point (at the bottom of the fore part of the PBB body) is 2.395 m below the waterline; if the sample vessel sails at $d = 1.149$ m, the lowest point corresponding to the 5°

heeling angle is 1.786 m below the waterline. Thus, at both draughts considered, the sample vessel equipped with the PBB bodies could avoid contact with the bottom only if the under-keel clearance is greater than ≈ 0.64 m, if its metacentric height corresponds to GM_{\min} determined in compliance with ES-TRIN intact stability requirements. Otherwise, to prevent grounding at low water levels, the minimum metacentric heights should be greater than the values reported in Table 4. The minimum metacentric heights necessary to maintain a desired under-keel clearance (in different water

depths, w_d), if the sample ship equipped with PBB is subjected to the heeling moments prescribed by the ES-TRIN rules, are given in Figure 5. With metacentric heights corresponding to uniform vertical distribution of cargo (given in Table 5) it would be (marginally) possible to avoid grounding even at the lowest water depths considered. (It should be, however, taken into account that the analysis is based on the loading conditions with 50% of supplies; thus, a certain margin should be accounted for when using the charts in Figure 5).

Figure 5. Minimum metacentric heights required to attain a certain under-keel clearance in case the sample ship subjected to heeling moments prescribed by the rules sails: (a) at $d = 1.753$ m with four container tiers, (b) at $d = 1.149$ m with four container tiers, (c) at $d = 1.753$ m with two container tiers, (d) at $d = 1.149$ m with two container tiers.

Another scenario which may be relevant in view of increased overall beam of the vessel and decreased width of the fairway is the stability of the vessel in case of a loss of one of the PBB bodies in intact condition. Such a loss may occur due to an allision with the fairway infrastructure or a bridge pillar, or a collision with another vessel. The calculations show that if the sample vessel sails with KG_{max}/GM_{min} reported in Table 4, the loss of one PBB body would lead to a total stability failure, in all the cases considered. Capsize and (partial) sinking in the shallow water would be followed by sliding and loss of non-secured containers.

Nevertheless, it was already emphasized that the values given in Table 4 comprise a considerable margin; in practice, the vertical center of gravity would be much lower. Thus, as a next step, the static angle of heel of the sample ship with the vertical center of gravity corresponding to uniform vertical distribution of cargo after the loss of one PBB body is calculated for all cases considered and reported in Table 6. If the sample ship sails at $d = 1.753$ m, the obtained values are well above the limiting 5° even prior to action of heeling moments prescribed by the rules, which could lead to the loss of non-secured cargo and subsequently, obstruction of navigation on the fairway.

Finally, it is examined which values of KG_{max}/GM_{min} would be sufficient to prevent the ship subjected to heeling moments defined by the rules from heeling for more than 5° after the loss of one PBB body. The results are reported in Table 7. The ship sailing at $d = 1.753$ m with one PBB body could not comply with the stability regulations with any positive value of KG because the heeling angles would be higher than the prescribed ones.

Table 6. Static angle of heel of the sample ship equipped with PBB, due to the loss of one PBB body, corresponding to uniform vertical distribution of the cargo; the draught corresponds to the floating position prior to the loss of a PBB body

d	tiers	KG	GM	KG_{cargo}	φ_s
1.753	4	4.444	5.31	5.782	10.7°
1.149	4	3.628	10.889	5.782	4.9°
1.753	2	2.732	7.023	3.191	8.2°
1.149	2	2.452	12.065	3.191	4.4°

In case that the examined ship sails at $d = 1.149$ m, generally it would be possible to limit the heeling angle to 5° after the loss of a PBB body in

the two-tier arrangement; as for the four-tier arrangement, the required KG_{max}/GM_{min} values are theoretically possible, but could not be practically attained with any vertical distribution of cargo mass reported in Table 2. It follows that the loss of one PBB body could be very dangerous and that the risk mitigation apparently could not be achieved with the stability-related operational measures (i.e., a favorable cargo distribution). Instead, it seems that the probability of loss of a PBB body should be reduced by suitable design measures.

Table 7. Maximum vertical center of gravity and minimum metacentric height of the sample ship equipped with PBB, and corresponding vertical center of gravity of the cargo, after the loss of one PBB body, determined in compliance with intact stability regulations of ES-TRIN (CESNI, 2023)

d	tiers	KG_{max}	GM_{min}	KG_{cargo}
1.753	4	/	/	/
1.149	4	1.997	12.520	2.188
1.753	2	/	/	/
1.149	2	2.541	11.977	3.386

Damage stability

Damage stability considerations bring forward the issue of subdivision of the PBB bodies. According to the procedure for deployment of PBB, the PBB bodies would have to be ballasted prior to being connected to the ship, so as to attain (at least) the operational draught of the ship (d_1 or d_2). In course of ballasting, however, an interesting phenomenon may take place: the loss of static longitudinal stability (“flipping”) of a cylindrical body with a free surface. It is found that the effective longitudinal metacentric height of the PBB body, which is not subdivided by means of transverse watertight bulkheads, would reach zero value during the ballasting at approximately $d_{PBB} = 1.563$ m. Considering that this draught is lower than $d_1 = 1.8$ m, it follows that the PBB body would have to be subdivided in the longitudinal direction. If the PBB body is divided into two watertight compartments by a single bulkhead placed lengthwise in the middle of the cylinder, the loss of the static longitudinal stability would not take place (almost) until the PBB body sinks, provided that the compartments are simultaneously ballasted. Nevertheless, such a simple subdivision would not be effective from the point of view of the damage stability of the ship equipped with PBB. Namely, in the application of the two-compartment standard, the damage of the single bulkhead would lead to

flooding of the entire PBB body. It follows that a higher degree of subdivision of the PBB bodies should be implemented. Therefore, in this study, the position of the transverse watertight bulkheads corresponds to the longitudinal subdivision of the ship, see Figure 6.

The outcomes of the damage stability calculations are reported in Table 8. It should be noted that number of container tiers does not affect the assessment of the KG_{max}/GM_{min} values from the damage stability point of view, which reduces the number of considered cases to two. Comparing the KG_{max}/GM_{min} values reported in Table 8 with the ones given in Table 4, it follows that the damage stability requirements are more stringent than the intact stability rules in all cases considered. Nevertheless, the required KG_{max}/GM_{min} values are practically attainable, as the minimum metacentric heights are still lower than the values which can be achieved by the uniform vertical distribution of the cargo (see Table 5).

Table 8. Maximum vertical center of gravity and minimum metacentric height of the sample ship equipped with PBB, and the corresponding vertical center of gravity of the cargo, determined in compliance with the damage stability regulations of ADN (UNECE, 2023)

d	tiers	KG_{max}	GM_{min}	KG_{cargo}
1.753	4/2	7.224	8.121	10.089
1.149	4/2	13.583	9.450	28.221

Finally, it is investigated if the flooding due to damage could lead to grounding. Metacentric heights necessary to maintain a targeted under-keel clearance following the most critical damage are reported in Figure 7. If the sample ship sails at $d = 1.753$ m, grounding would be inevitable in all examined water depths except in $w_d = 2.4$ m. The prospects slightly improve at $d = 1.149$ m, when grounding could be avoided with realistic metacentric heights in $w_d > 1.6$ m.

Figure 6. Subdivision of the PBB bodies

(a)

(b)

Figure 7. Minimum metacentric heights required to maintain a certain under-keel clearance after the most critical damage in case the sample ship sails: (a) at $d = 1.753$ m, (b) at $d = 1.149$ m

As stated previously, the positive influence of PBB on intact stability could have been expected. The influence of PBB on stability in damaged condition, however, is not that straightforward. Namely, due to prescribed transverse extent of damage, the bottom damage cases may comprise both the compartments in the double bottom and the PBB body. These damage cases prove to be the critical ones and, as such, form the primary drivers of the damage stability assessment. At the same time, bottom damages are precisely the ones which are more likely to happen in extreme low-water conditions.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In extremely low water levels, the cargo-carrying capacity and the propulsive efficiency of inland vessels are decreased, freight rates are increased and the reliability of the whole supply chain is questioned. Additional buoyancy bodies may improve some of these aspects, but their use is intrinsically related to hazards atypical for regular navigation conditions. To get an insight into the potential safety issues of inland container vessels equipped with additional buoyancy bodies in extremely low-water navigation conditions, intact and damage stability assessment of a standard Large Rhine container ship equipped with the pipe-based buoyancy (PBB) bodies was performed following the requirements of the applicable stability regulations: ES-TRIN (CESNI, 2023) and ADN (UNECE, 2023).

As it may have been expected, the sample ship with the PBB bodies could fulfill the intact stability requirements of the applicable regulations with a considerable margin. The damage stability requirements were more stringent than intact stability rules in all the investigated cases; yet the required KG_{\max}/GM_{\min} values are attainable with the standard cargo loading practices. Nevertheless, as the water depth is not considered in the stability rules of ES-TRIN and ADN, the minimum metacentric heights determined in compliance with these regulations provide no guarantee against contact with the river bottom / grounding in low water levels. On the other hand, considering that the value of under-keel clearance is not formally restricted, it is up to the Master to decide whether to sail or not in given environmental and loading conditions. An analysis akin to defining

“operational limitations”, presented in this paper (see Figure 5 and Figure 7) could assist the Masters in a “risk-informed” planning of the voyage. The requirement to perform the damage stability calculations seems to be particularly relevant, in specific because the ships, such as the one examined in this paper, are not subject to mandatory damage stability assessment unless they carry dangerous goods.

Depending on the draught and the loading condition of the ship equipped with PBB, the loss of one PBB body (in intact condition), could lead to a total stability failure, partial sinking and grounding of the vessel, loss of cargo, and consequently, obstruction of navigation. The analysis presented in the paper indicates that the loss of a PBB body cannot be satisfactorily solved by stability-related operational measures.

Considering that more frequent and more extreme low-water navigation conditions could be expected in the future, it seems that the applicable regulatory framework should be updated as well, and the underlying risks should be reexamined.

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